

1 **Longitudinal associations of air pollution and green space with cardiometabolic**
2 **risk factor clustering among children in the Netherlands**

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30 **Abstract**

31 **Background:** This study examines longitudinal associations of air pollution and green space with
32 cardiometabolic risk among children in the Netherlands.

33 **Methods:** Three Dutch prospective cohorts with a total of 13,822 participants aged 5 to 17 years were
34 included: (1) the Amsterdam Born Children and their Development (ABCD) study from Amsterdam
35 (n=2,547), (2) the Generation R study from Rotterdam (n=5,431), and (3) the Lifelines study from
36 northern Netherlands (n=5,844). Air pollution (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, and elemental carbon (EC)) and green
37 space exposures (density in multiple Euclidean buffer sizes) from 2006 to 2017 at home address level
38 were used. Cardiometabolic risk factor clustering was assessed by a MetScore, which was derived from
39 a confirmatory factor analysis of six cardiometabolic risk factors to assess the overall risk. Linear
40 regression models with change in Metscore as the dependent variable, adjusted for multiple confounders,
41 were conducted for each cohort separately. Meta-analyses were used to pool cohort-specific estimates.

42 **Results:** Exposure to higher levels of NO₂ and EC was significantly associated with increases in
43 MetScore in Lifelines (per SD higher exposure: β_{NO_2} =0.006, 95% CI=0.001 to 0.010; β_{EC} =0.008, 95%
44 CI=0.002 to 0.014). In the other two cohort studies, these associations were in the same direction but
45 these were not significant. Higher green space density in 500-meter buffer zones around participants'
46 residential addresses was not significantly associated with decreases of MetScore in all three cohorts.
47 Higher green space density in 2000-meter buffer zones was significantly associated with decreases of
48 MetScore in ABCD and Lifelines (per SD higher green space density: β_{ABCD} =-0.008, 95% CI=-0.013 to
49 -0.003; $\beta_{\text{Lifelines}}$ =-0.002, 95% CI=-0.003 to -0.00003). The pooled estimates were β_{NO_2} =0.003 (95% CI=-
50 0.001 to 0.006) for NO₂, β_{EC} =0.003 (95% CI=-0.001, 0.007) for EC, and $\beta_{\text{500m buffer}}$ =-0.0014 (95% CI=-
51 0.0026 to -0.0001) for green space.

52 **Conclusions:** More green space exposure at residence was associated with decreased cardiometabolic
53 risk in children. Exposure to more NO₂ and EC was also associated with increased cardiometabolic risk.

54 **Keywords:** Cardiometabolic diseases, Environmental health, Cohort study, Pediatrics

55

56 **Introduction**

57 Cardiometabolic risk factors are the largest contributors to the global disease burden (GBD 2017 Risk
58 Factor Collaborators, 2018). In terms of disability-adjusted life-years, high systolic blood pressure (SBP),
59 high fasting plasma glucose, high Body Mass Index (BMI), and high low-density lipoprotein cholesterol
60 (LDL-C) were among the top 10 risk factors in 2017 (GBD 2017 Risk Factor Collaborators, 2018).
61 Although cardiometabolic diseases (CMDs) occur most frequently among middle-aged and older adults,
62 cardiometabolic risk factor clustering has been shown to be stable from childhood into adulthood (Camhi
63 and Katzmarzyk, 2010), which emphasizes that risk factors in early life have later life consequences
64 (Hoffman et al., 2017).

65 Exposure to environmental characteristics, such as air pollution and green space, may be important
66 factors of cardiometabolic alterations among children (Araujo, 2011; Giorgini et al., 2016; Kuo, 2015;
67 Markevych et al., 2017a). Exposure to higher levels of air pollution may negatively impact
68 cardiometabolic health through autonomic nervous system imbalance, pulmonary and systemic
69 inflammation, and oxidative stress (Araujo, 2011; Giorgini et al., 2016). Children are suggested to be
70 more vulnerable to the harmful effects of air pollutants than adults, because their immune system is still
71 evolving and because they inhale a higher volume of air pollutants per body weight than adults (Salvi,
72 2007). On the contrary, green space may improve cardiometabolic health by its restoration and building
73 capacities (Kuo, 2015; Markevych et al., 2017a). For restoration, green space relieves psychological
74 stress (Kuo, 2015), which is associated with cardiometabolic diseases (Turner et al., 2020). For building,
75 green space releases certain chemical agents with cardiometabolic health implications (e.g., phytoncides)
76 (Kuo, 2015). It also has an indirect effect on cardiometabolic health. Specifically, green space can reduce
77 harm from exposure to air pollution, heat, and noise, and can encourage healthy lifestyle like outdoor
78 physical activity (Markevych et al., 2017a).

79 Previous evidence on the associations of air pollution and green space with cardiometabolic risk among
80 children is limited and inconsistent. A nationwide school-based study in Iran investigated the association
81 between air quality and individual cardiometabolic risk factors, and found significant positive
82 associations for SBP, total cholesterol, and triglycerides (TG) (Poursafa et al., 2014). A study in Spain
83 showed that the distance from home to green spaces was not significantly associated with
84 cardiometabolic risk in primary students (Gutiérrez-Zornoza et al., 2015). Another study did not provide
85 evidence for beneficial effects of green space or adverse effects of air pollution on cardiometabolic health
86 in Dutch adolescents (Bloemsma et al., 2019). These three studies are all based on cross-sectional designs,
87 thus a longitudinal study to provide evidence of a temporal relationship is merited.

88 Previous studies focused on individual cardiometabolic risk factors or sum of standardized scores (z-
89 scores) (Bloemsma et al., 2019; Gutiérrez-Zornoza et al., 2015; Poursafa et al., 2014), which are not ideal
90 indicators of overall cardiometabolic risk (Magge et al., 2017). An alternative indicator is metabolic
91 syndrome (MetS), which is a standard measure in adults referring to the presence of at least three of the
92 following five conditions: abdominal obesity, high blood pressure (BP), high blood glucose, high serum
93 TG, and low serum high-density lipoprotein (HDL-C) (Kaur, 2014). More than 40 unique definitions of
94 MetS have been identified in literature (Ford and Li, 2008). However, to date, there is no consensus on
95 whether MetS should be defined in pediatric populations and, if defined, which definition to use (Magge
96 et al., 2017). Furthermore, studies found that the diagnosis of MetS is highly unstable and fluctuates

97 throughout childhood (Goodman et al., 2007; Stanley et al., 2014). Thus its predictive value of future
98 risk is unclear (Magge et al., 2017).

99 To address these issues, it has been recommended to focus on cardiometabolic risk clustering, and to use
100 a continuous latent variable of cardiometabolic risk score, such as MetScore (Magge et al., 2017). The
101 MetScore as a continuum has been demonstrated to better predict adult risk from early adolescence as
102 compared to MetS or summed z-scores (Camhi and Katzmarzyk, 2010; Kelly et al., 2011; Magge et al.,
103 2017). To our knowledge, this new approach has not been previously used to analyse the association of
104 air pollution and green space with cardiometabolic risk. The current study aimed to examine the
105 prospective associations of air pollution and green space density with cardiometabolic risk factor
106 clustering among children in the Netherlands. It was hypothesized that higher exposure levels of air
107 pollution and green space are associated with a higher and lower MetScore among children in the
108 Netherlands, respectively.

109 **Methods**

110 **Study populations**

111 Data were derived from three Dutch population-based prospective cohort studies: Amsterdam Born
112 Children and their Development (ABCD) study, Generation R study, and Lifelines. All three cohort
113 studies have been described in detail previously (Kooijman et al., 2016; Scholtens et al., 2015; Van
114 Eijsden et al., 2011). The three cohort studies were approved by the Ethical Review Boards of the
115 respective institutions, and written informed consent from participants were obtained by each cohort
116 study.

117 The ABCD study is a prospective cohort study with the aim to examine the associations of maternal and
118 early-life conditions with children's health (Van Eijsden et al., 2011). In brief, between January 2003
119 and March 2004, all pregnant women (n=12,373) in Amsterdam attending their first prenatal visit were
120 invited to participate in the study. Mothers of singleton infants were contacted for follow-up
121 measurements. The current study included data from two follow-up waves when children from this
122 pregnancy were about five (2009) and eleven (2015-2016) years old, respectively.

123 The Generation R study is a population-based prospective cohort study from early pregnancy onwards
124 in Rotterdam, aiming to identify early environmental and genetic determinants of growth, development
125 and health from foetal life until young adulthood. (Kooijman et al., 2016). All pregnant women living in
126 the study area with a delivery date between April 2002 and January 2006 were invited to participate,
127 resulting in 9,778 mothers and their children enrolled in the study. The current study included data from
128 two follow-up waves when children were about five (2007-2011) and nine (2011-2015) years old,
129 respectively.

130 The Lifelines study is a multi-disciplinary prospective cohort study examining in a unique three-
131 generation design the health and health-related behaviours of 167,729 persons living in three northern
132 provinces of the Netherlands (Groningen, Friesland and Drenthe) (Scholtens et al., 2015). It employs a
133 broad range of investigative procedures in assessing the biomedical, socio-demographic, behavioural,
134 physical, and psychological factors which contribute to the health and disease of the general population,

135 with a special focus on multi-morbidity and complex genetics. The current study included data from
136 baseline (2007-2013) – with children aged 8 to 17 years – and the first follow-up wave (2014-2017).

137 Combining the three cohorts resulted in a study sample size of 14,097 (ABCD: 2,811; Generation R:
138 5,431; and Lifelines: 5,855) children aged 5 to 17 years who attended both surveys. Of those participants,
139 18 (ABCD: 7; and Lifelines: 11) participants were excluded because they had a history of diabetes,
140 hypertension, stroke, heart disease, or disease precocious puberty, and 257 (ABCD: 257) participants
141 were excluded because they used certain medication that may influence the cardiometabolic risk factor
142 levels (medication with ATC codes (ATC Code, 2023): B01, C01, H01, H02, J01, D06, H03, and M01).
143 The analytical sample included 13,822 participants (ABCD: 2,547; Generation R: 5,431; and Lifelines:
144 5,844).

145 **Exposure assessment**

146 Data on air pollution and green space were obtained from the Geoscience and Health Cohort Consortium
147 (GECCO) (Lakerveld et al., 2020; Timmermans et al., 2018). The environmental exposure data at the
148 home address-level were linked to participants.

149 Data on annual average outdoor concentrations of particulate matter with diameters $<2.5 \mu\text{m}$ ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$) and
150 $<10.0 \mu\text{m}$ (PM_{10}), nitrogen dioxide (NO_2), and elemental carbon (EC) were modeled by the Institute for
151 Public Health and the Environment (Velders et al., 2011; Wesseling et al., 2015). These data were based
152 on a combination of dispersion and chemical transport model calculations and measurements from
153 National Air Quality monitoring locations. Data were available on $1 \times 1 \text{ km}$ resolution from 2006 to 2017
154 annually, and on $25 \times 25 \text{ m}$ resolution from 2013 to 2017 annually. The data in $1 \times 1 \text{ km}$ resolution were
155 used to back-extrapolate data in $25 \times 25 \text{ m}$ resolution for years before 2013 (Chen et al., 2010). We scaled
156 $25 \times 25 \text{ m}$ map in 2013 by ratio of the $1 \times 1 \text{ km}$ map of the years prior to 2013 to the $1 \times 1 \text{ km}$ map in 2013,
157 and assumed this to be applicable to all $25 \times 25 \text{ m}$ grids in a $1 \times 1 \text{ km}$ grid.

158 Residential green space exposure was assessed by green space density. This refers to the percentage of
159 area devoted to green space (i.e., parks, public gardens, forests, graveyards, and agriculture) within a
160 Euclidean buffer (radii of 150, 250, 350, 500, 750, 1000, 1650, and 2000 m) around residential addresses.
161 These data were based on the land area coverage statistics from Statistics Netherlands (Statistics
162 Netherlands, 2024), and were available for 2006, 2008, 2010, 2012, and 2015. Applying situational
163 interpretation on all available sources, a minimum lower limit of 1 hectare was used for green space
164 (Statistics Netherlands, 2024). Both air pollution and green space data were used by averaging over the
165 study period corresponding to each cohort.

166 **Assessment of cardiometabolic risk factors**

167 Assessed cardiometabolic risk factors for deriving the MetScore consisted of total cholesterol, HDL-C,
168 TG, BMI, SBP, and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) (**Figure 1**). The measurement methods for each
169 cohort are described in **Appendix 1**.

170 **Calculation of MetScore**

171 A consistent confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted in a pooled dataset to derive the
172 MetScore across all cohorts. CFA allows for the testing of hypotheses or theories about the relationships
173 between observed variables and their underlying latent constructs (Harrington, 2009). In the current study,

174 it was used to validate the MetScore, ensuring that MetScore adequately represents the six component
175 cardiometabolic risk factors (Harrington, 2009). BMI was standardized by age and sex using LMS tables
176 (Lambda for the skew, Mu for the median, and Sigma for the generalized coefficient of variation (Cole,
177 1990)) from a Dutch nationwide growth study (Schönbeck et al., 2011) and a German cohort study
178 (Rönnecke et al., 2019), respectively. The SBP and DBP were standardized by age and sex using LMS
179 tables from a reference for Caucasian children (Wühl et al., 2002). TG was log-transformed because its
180 distribution was skewed. The reciprocal of HDL-C was used when standardizing so that the interpretation
181 of higher factor loading scores is the same with other measures. Subsequently, the z-scores for all CFA
182 components were created.

183 The goodness of fit indices included the Comparative Fit Index (good fit: CFI, ≥ 0.90), the Tucker-Lewis
184 Index (good fit: TLI, ≥ 0.90), the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (good fit: RMSEA, ≤ 0.06),
185 and the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (good fit: SRMR, < 0.08) (Hu and Bentler, 1999). The
186 standardized factor loadings were used to calculate the factor score of MetScore for each participant,
187 separately. This score can be interpreted as a z-score, the value is positively correlated with
188 cardiometabolic risk and where zero indicates the population mean.

189 **Covariates**

190 Based on confounders used in previous studies (Bloemsma et al., 2019; Poursafa et al., 2014; Shenassa
191 and Williams, 2020), a directed acyclic graph was created to choose confounders (**Appendix Figure S1**).
192 At two surveys of each cohort, participants' parents provided information about age, sex (male, female),
193 ethnicity (Dutch, Non-western other, Western other), parental education level (low to low-intermediate,
194 high-intermediate, high), maternal smoking during pregnancy (no, < 1 a day, ≥ 1 a day), child screen time
195 (< 1 hour a day, 1 to 2 hours a day, > 2 hours a day), child leisure time physical activity (< 1 hour a week,
196 1 to 2 hours a week, 2 to 4 hours a week, > 4 hours a week), parental marital status (married / live together,
197 divorced / don't live together), and year of birth. The duration between these two surveys was also
198 obtained. Urbanization degree within a Euclidean buffer of 1 km around each address was obtained from
199 GECCO (Lakerveld et al., 2020; Timmermans et al., 2018). Objectively measured neighborhood
200 socioeconomic status (SES) scores were obtained from the Netherlands Institute for Social Research
201 (Netherlands Institute for Social Research, 2023). These scores are based on the average income, the
202 percentage of residents with a low income, the percentage of residents with a low level of education, and
203 the percentage of unemployed residents in the neighborhood (Netherlands Institute for Social Research,
204 2023). Higher scores indicate higher area-level SES.

205 **Statistical analysis**

206 Characteristics of the study sample and the area-level exposure measures were presented using
207 descriptive statistics for each cohort, separately. The relative variability between exposures was
208 compared by coefficient of variation, which is calculated by dividing the standard deviation by the mean
209 and then multiplying by 100. The average of environmental exposures across years (air pollution with
210 25×25 m resolution and green space density in 500 m, 1000 m, and 2000 m buffers) were calculated and
211 used in longitudinal analyses. Since all three cohorts have two waves of measurements, the change of
212 MetScore between the two waves was used as dependent variable. Linear regression models were
213 conducted for the association between average environmental exposure over time and change of
214 MetScore over time. Models were adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, baseline MetScore, highest parental
215 education level, maternal smoking during pregnancy, screen time, leisure time physical activity, parental

216 marital status, year of birth, duration between two surveys, neighborhood SES score, and urbanization
217 degree. For sensitivity analyses, mutual confounding between air pollution and green space exposure
218 was further considered in models by adjusting for each other. Air pollution with 1×1 km resolution across
219 all years and green space density in other Euclidean buffer sizes (radii of 150, 250, 350, 750, and 1650m)
220 were also modelled in sensitivity analyses. In all analyses, unit of air pollution and green space were per
221 standard deviation (SD).

222 Within each cohort, multiple imputation was conducted to deal with missing data. For each variable with
223 missing values, the specified imputation model replaced missing values with values randomly drawn
224 from the predictive distribution of the variable conditional on other observed data. This process created
225 multiple imputed datasets with no missing values that reflected the uncertainty of missing data. All
226 variables in the analytical model were included in the imputation model. We generated twenty imputed
227 datasets that were analysed separately and pooled the estimates based on Rubin's rules (Van Buuren,
228 2018). Lastly, random-effect meta-analyses were conducted to synthesize the results from the three
229 cohorts. The I^2 statistic was obtained as a measure of heterogeneity across cohorts. All analyses were
230 performed using R software (Liu et al., 2021). Statistical significance was defined as $P < 0.05$ (2-sided).

231

232 **Results**

233 The characteristics at baseline of the study sample and the area-level exposure measures for each cohort
 234 are presented in **Table 1**. The mean ages at baseline were 5.5 ± 0.5 years for ABCD, 6.1 ± 0.5 years for
 235 Generation R, and 9.5 ± 2.7 years for Lifelines, respectively. The percentages of male participants were
 236 50.4% for ABCD, 49.9% for Generation R, and 48.6% for Lifelines. Participants in Lifelines were mostly
 237 ethnically Dutch (96.6%), while Generation R had more ethnical diversity (Dutch: 58.0%). Participants
 238 in ABCD had more children with high parental education level (75.9%) and more parents divorced or
 239 not living together (17.4%). Participants in Generation R had more events of maternal smoking during
 240 pregnancy. Children in Lifelines had more screen time and underwent more physical activities during
 241 leisure time. Participants in ABCD had higher neighborhood SES score. Participants in ABCD and
 242 Generation R mostly lived in urban areas while participants in Lifelines mostly lived in rural areas.
 243 Participants in Lifelines were generally exposed to less air pollution and more green space at residence.
 244 The coefficient of variations ranged from 5.5% to 8.2% for particulate matter, and ranged from 13.9% to
 245 20% for NO₂ and EC. **Appendix Figure S1** shows the Spearman correlations between green space and
 246 air pollutants in the three cohorts, respectively. Green space density was moderately, negatively
 247 correlated with air pollutants ($r=-0.39$ to -0.62), expect for particulate matter in Lifelines ($r=-0.10$ to -
 248 0.12).

249 **Table 1.** Characteristics of participants by cohorts.

Variables ¹	Cohorts		
	ABCD 2009-2016	Generation R 2007-2015	Lifelines 2007-2017
n	2,547	5,431	5,844
Age at baseline (year)	5.5 ± 0.5	6.1 ± 0.5	9.5 ± 2.7
Male (%)	50.4	49.9	48.6
Ethnicity (%)			
Dutch	73.7	58.0	96.6
Non-western other	13.0	15.2	2.0
Western other	13.4	26.8	1.4
Highest parental education level (%)			
Low to Low-intermediate	7.7	15.2	8.4
High-intermediate	16.5	26.8	41.7
High	75.9	58.1	49.9
Maternal smoking during pregnancy (%)			
No	93.0	73.2	90.4
<1 a day	2.3	4.5	0.9
≥1 a day	4.7	22.4	8.7
Child Screen time (%)			
<1 hour a day	38.1	42.7	15.8
1 to 2 hours a day	46.2	40.1	36.8
>2 hours a day	15.7	17.3	47.5
Child Leisure time physical activity (%)			
<1 hour a week	10.5	5.3	2.5

1 to 2 hours a week	19.4	27.7	3.5
2 to 4 hours a week	33.1	44.1	60.2
>4 hours a week	37.0	22.8	33.9
Parental marital status (%)			
Married / live together	82.6	88.9	93.7
Divorced / don't live together	17.4	11.1	6.3
Neighborhood socio-economic status score ²	0.6 (-0.5, 1.3)	-0.4 (-1.3, 1.2)	-0.5 (-1.4, 0.2)
Residence density (addresses per km ²)	2,529 (1,566, 5,698)	2,629 (1,604, 4,605)	449 (171, 913)
Urbanicity degree (%)			
Non-urban (<500 addresses per km ²)	4.5	2.8	53.6
Limited urban (500-1000 addresses per km ²)	7.7	7.9	25.4
Moderately urban (1000-1500 addresses per km ²)	10.4	11.5	12.4
Strong urban (1500-2500 addresses per km ²)	26.8	25.0	6.2
Very strong urban (≥2500 addresses per km ²)	50.7	52.8	2.5
Duration between two surveys (years)	6.1 ± 0.5	3.7 ± 0.5	2.9 ± 0.8
Average PM _{2.5} concentration (µg/m ³)	15.1 ± 1.2	15.8 ± 1.3	9.5 ± 0.7
Average PM ₁₀ concentration (µg/m ³)	23.4 ± 1.7	24.3 ± 1.7	16.3 ± 0.9
Average NO ₂ concentration (µg/m ³)	25.5 ± 4.5	31.2 ± 4.5	12.2 ± 1.7
Average elemental carbon concentration (µg/m ³)	1.1 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.2	0.5 ± 0.1
Average Green space density in 1 km buffer (percentage) ³	18.8 ± 15.9	16.5 ± 13.7	54.1 ± 26.8
Average Agriculture density in 1 km buffer (percentage)	8.7 ± 16.0	7.4 ± 12.9	46.9 ± 29.2
Baseline MetScore ⁴			
Total cholesterol (mmol/L)	4.0 ± 0.7	4.2 ± 0.6	4.1 ± 0.7
High-density lipoprotein (mmol/L)	1.3 ± 0.3	1.4 ± 0.3	1.6 ± 0.3
Triglyceride (mmol/L)	0.7 ± 0.3	1.0 ± 0.5	0.7 ± 0.4
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	15.5 ± 1.4	16.2 ± 1.9	18.7 ± 3.2
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	98.4 ± 8.5	103.3 ± 8.0	106.4 ± 10.8
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	59.1 ± 8.2	61.4 ± 6.7	59.5 ± 6.3
Change of MetScore	0.01 ± 0.06	-0.01 ± 0.05	0.01 ± 0.05

250 ¹ Values are mean ± SD or median (first quartile, third quartile) for continuous variables and % for
251 categorical variables. The values for environmental exposures have been averaged over the study
252 period corresponding to each cohort.

253 ² This score is based on the average income, the percentage of residents with a low income, the
254 percentage of residents with a low level of education, and the percentage of unemployed residents in
255 the neighborhood.

256 ³ Green space are aggregates of parks, public gardens, forests, graveyards, and agriculture.

257 ⁴ Cardiometabolic risk factor clustering, derived from a factor analysis of six components: total
258 cholesterol, HDL-C, TG, BMI, SBP, and DBP. All in z-scores.

259

260 **Figure 1** presents the model fit indices and factor loadings of the CFA model of MetScore. The model
 261 fit indices overall showed good fit. All components were significantly contributing to the MetScore.
 262 The variance in MetScore was mostly explained by BMI z score (46.9%, the square of the standardized
 263 factor loadings).

264 **Figure 1.** Factor loadings for cardiometabolic risk factor clustering (MetScore), combining data from the
 265 first waves of three cohorts: ABCD, Generation R and Lifelines. All components are standardized into
 266 z-scores. Abbreviations: CFI= Comparative Fit Index, TLI=Tucker-Lewis Index, RMSEA=Root Mean
 267 Square Error of Approximation, SRMR=Standardized Root Mean Square Residual.

268 The associations of air pollution and green space exposure with change of MetScore for each separate
 269 cohort are shown in **Table 2**. There is no multicollinearity problem in the models. After adjusting for
 270 multiple confounders, exposures to higher levels of NO₂ and EC were significantly associated with
 271 increases of MetScore in Lifelines (per SD higher exposure: β_{NO_2} =0.006, 95% CI=0.001 to 0.010; β_{EC}
 272 =0.008, 95% CI=0.002 to 0.014). In ABCD and Generation R, these associations were in the same
 273 direction, but these were not statistically significant. The associations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ with change of
 274 MetScore were not significant in all three cohorts. Higher green space density in 500-meter buffer zones
 275 around participants' residential address was significantly associated with decreases of MetScore in
 276 ABCD and Lifelines (per SD higher green space: β_{ABCD} =-0.003, 95% CI=-0.011 to 0.005; $\beta_{\text{Lifelines}}$ =-0.001,
 277 95% CI=-0.003 to 0.00004). All observed associations were not significant in Generation R. In sensitivity
 278 analyses, after considering mutual confounding between air pollution and green space, or modeling in
 279 another resolution (i.e., 1×1 km) and other buffer sizes (i.e., 150, 250, 350, 750, and 1650 m), models
 280 showed similar results (**Appendix Table S1-S3**).

281 **Figure 2** presents the meta-analyses of results from three cohorts. The pooled estimates were 0.003 (95%
 282 CI=-0.001 to 0.006; $P=0.13$) for NO₂, 0.003 (95% CI=-0.001, 0.007; $P=0.13$) for EC, and -0.0014 (95%

283 CI=-0.0026 to -0.0001; $P=0.03$) for green space in 500-meter buffer zones. The pooled estimates were
284 marginally significant for green space in other buffer zones, but were not significant for particulate matter.

285

Table 2. Linear relation between air pollution, green space exposure and change of cardiometabolic risk factor clustering (MetScore)^{1,2}

Exposure	Change of MetScore in ABCD, n=2,547		Change of MetScore in Generation R, n=5,431		Change of MetScore in Lifelines, n=5,844	
	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i>	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i>	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i>
PM _{2.5} concentration	0.0001 (-0.006, 0.006)	0.98	0.001 (-0.001, 0.004)	0.25	-0.0003 (-0.004, 0.003)	0.86
PM ₁₀ concentration	0.0005 (-0.005, 0.006)	0.86	0.001 (-0.001, 0.003)	0.31	-0.001 (-0.005, 0.002)	0.50
NO ₂ concentration	0.003 (-0.003, 0.009)	0.39	0.001 (-0.001, 0.003)	0.43	0.006 (0.001, 0.010)*	0.02
Elemental carbon concentration	0.003 (-0.004, 0.009)	0.42	0.001 (-0.002, 0.004)	0.48	0.008 (0.002, 0.014)*	0.01
Green space density in 500 m buffer	-0.003 (-0.011, 0.005)	0.46	-0.001 (-0.004, 0.002)	0.46	-0.001 (-0.003, 0.00004)	0.06
Green space density in 1000 m buffer	-0.007 (-0.013, -0.0005)*	0.04	-0.001 (-0.004, 0.003)	0.64	-0.001 (-0.003, 0.0002)	0.08
Green space density in 2000 m buffer	-0.008 (-0.013, -0.003)**	0.003	-0.001 (-0.004, 0.002)	0.45	-0.002 (-0.003, -0.00003)*	0.048

286

¹ Unit of air pollution is per standard deviation (SD) based on data of a resolution of 25×25 m raster. Unit of green space is per SD. The SDs were 1.1, 1.4, 3.6, 0.2, 21.1, 20.6, and 19.0 for PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, elemental carbon, and green space in 500 m buffer, 1000 m buffer, and 2000 m buffer, respectively.

287

288

² Models adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, baseline MetScore, highest parental education level, maternal smoking during pregnancy, screen time, leisure time physical activity, parental marital status, year of birth, duration between two surveys, neighborhood socioeconomic status score, and residence density.

289

290

P* < 0.05, *P* < 0.01, ****P* < 0.001

291

(1) PM2.5

(5) Green space in 500 m buffer

(2) PM10

(6) Green space in 1 km buffer

(3) NO2

(7) Green space in 2 km buffer

(4) Soot

292 **Figure 2.** Meta-analyses of linear associations of air pollution and green space exposure with change of
293 cardiometabolic risk factor clustering in children participating in three Dutch cohort studies. Unit of air
294 pollution is per standard deviation (SD) based on data of a resolution of 25×25 m raster. Unit of green

295 space is per SD. The SDs were 1.1, 1.4, 3.6, 0.2, 21.1, 20.6, and 19.0 for PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, elemental
296 carbon, and green space in 500 m buffer, 1000 m buffer, and 2000 m buffer, respectively.

297 **Discussion**

298 More green space exposure at residence was associated with decreased cardiometabolic risk as measured
299 by MetScore over time among children. Results for air pollution were inconsistent among pollution
300 indicators. Higher concentrations of NO₂ and EC were associated with increased cardiometabolic risk in
301 Lifelines. The pooled estimates were marginally significant for NO₂ and EC. There was no statistical
302 evidence found for the association of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ with cardiometabolic risk. Results are robust after
303 considering mutual confounding between air pollution and green space, or modeling in other resolution
304 and buffer sizes.

305 The current results strengthen the evidence of a protective effect of green space exposure against
306 cardiometabolic risk among children. Several previous studies reported associations between green space
307 exposure and individual cardiometabolic risk factors among children, like lower BMI (Bell et al., 2008;
308 Wolch et al., 2011) and lower BP (Zhao et al., 2022). However, to the best of our knowledge, this is the
309 first study that found a significant association for overall cardiometabolic risk. A previous study in The
310 Netherlands did not find an association between green space and overall cardiometabolic risk at ages 12
311 and 16 years, respectively (Bloemsma et al., 2019). Neither a Spanish study in rural areas found an
312 association between distance from children's home to green space and overall risk (Gutiérrez-Zornoza et
313 al., 2015). Both studies applied a cross-sectional design, and both studies measured the overall risk by
314 summing the z-scores of individual risk factors, which gives equal weight to components. Instead, the
315 current study used a prospective design and derived a MetScore by a CFA of component risk factors,
316 which takes the weight of separate components into account, as recommended (Magge et al., 2017).
317 Therefore, the present study expands the current literature and strengthens the evidence base on the
318 association between green space and cardiometabolic risk among children.

319 For air pollution, there was large heterogeneity among the current study and previous ones. A study in
320 the Netherlands investigated the associations of PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, and NO₂ at residence with overall
321 cardiometabolic risk (summed z-scores), and found no significant results (Bloemsma et al., 2019). A
322 national study in the US used residential concentrations of volatile organic compounds as indicator of air
323 pollution and found an elevated overall risk (summed z-scores) (Shenassa and Williams, 2020). A study
324 in China investigated the PM_{2.5} constituents at school in relation to MetS and indicated a robust
325 association for EC (Li et al., 2023). All of them were cross-sectional studies among children. The current
326 prospective study found evidence for NO₂ and EC, but not for particulate matter.

327 Even when using the same exposure and overall risk measures in the current study, there was large
328 heterogeneity among the three cohorts (**Table 1**). For example, Generation R was more ethnically diverse
329 while Lifelines is predominantly Dutch. Children in Generation R were more predisposed to
330 cardiometabolic risk because more mothers smoked during pregnancy. Children in ABCD lived in
331 neighborhoods characterized by a substantially higher SES. Children in Lifelines mostly lived in rural
332 areas, while children in ABCD and Generation R mostly lived in strong urban areas. However, this
333 heterogeneity cannot be addressed by meta-regression since there is a small number of studies. The

334 credibility of the current results from meta-analysis is low. We therefore emphasize to interpret the results
335 of the meta-analyses with caution.

336 Literature has proposed several mechanisms that green space exposure may decrease cardiometabolic
337 risk. As discussed earlier, green space can release certain chemical agents like phytoncides that directly
338 inhibit inflammation (Day, 2012), which is associated with cardiometabolic health in the long term. Apart
339 from direct effect, green space may indirectly benefit cardiometabolic health by releasing stress,
340 encouraging physical activity and depositing air pollution (Markevych et al., 2017b). Therefore, air
341 pollution may play a role as a mediator in the association between green space and cardiometabolic risk.
342 It has been recommended in a recent review that primary study should consider interrelationships
343 between these built environment aspects in relation to cardiometabolic risk (Liu et al., 2023). The current
344 study included mutual confounding of air pollution and green space in models and found their
345 independent associations with cardiometabolic risk. However, simply adjusting for each other does not
346 address the interrelationship since there could partially be a mediation effect, a moderation effect, or both.
347 Future studies should investigate the mediation and moderation effects, while taking into account the
348 types of green space, because vegetation of different heights may interact with air pollution differently
349 (Jim and Chen, 2008).

350 The current study found an increasing risk for NO₂ and EC, but not for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. Statistic
351 description showed that particulate matter exposures had small variation within cohorts while NO₂ and
352 EC exposures had larger variation. This small variation within cohorts could impede the finding of
353 significant associations. Another potential explanation is that particulate matter comprises a wide range
354 of particles. Some particles may be less associated with cardiometabolic health, but may be more related
355 to allergy and respiratory issues, like pollen and spores (Idrose et al., 2022; Tham et al., 2014). Other
356 particles, such as EC, are more strongly associated with cardiometabolic risk (Song et al., 2022). Both
357 NO₂ and EC are primarily produced by combustion processes, particularly in vehicles, power plants, and
358 industrial facilities. EC is generated by the incomplete combustion of carbon-based fuels (Niranjan and
359 Thakur, 2017). In the context of the Netherlands, NO₂ and EC are mostly traffic-related diesel exhaust.
360 Randomized trials showed that their exposures are associated with acute endothelial dysfunction and
361 vasoconstriction in vivo (Mills et al., 2005; Peretz et al., 2008), which in turn can increase
362 cardiometabolic risk.

363 **Strengths and limitations**

364 The current study has several strengths, including a relatively large sample size as compared to previous
365 studies, use of a longitudinal design and applying a recommended MetScore to assess overall
366 cardiometabolic risk among children. There are also several limitations to consider when interpreting the
367 results. First, there was little variability in the environmental exposures which impede the finding of
368 significance. Second, the exposures were only measured at residence in the current study. The mobility
369 of individuals should be considered in future study including exposures at school and commute
370 (Ntarladima et al., 2019). Third, due to data availability across three cohorts, the MetScore was
371 constructed based on an incomplete list of components. Future study should add other components like
372 fasting glucose and HbA1c. Lastly, due to the small number of studies included, heterogeneity cannot be
373 addressed via a meta-regression.

374 **Conclusion**

375 Among children, more green space exposure at residence was associated with decreased cardiometabolic
376 risk over time. Some evidence was found for the association between air pollution and increased
377 cardiometabolic risk. Exposure to higher concentrations of NO₂ and EC was associated with increased
378 cardiometabolic risk in the Lifelines cohort. No evidence was found for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀, probably due
379 to the small variations in exposures. More research is needed to investigate the longitudinal effect of air
380 pollution and green space on cardiometabolic risk among children; this should involve application of the
381 MetScore and consideration of the interrelationship between exposure measures.

382

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418

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Appendices of

Longitudinal associations of air pollution and green space with cardiometabolic risk factor clustering among children in the Netherlands

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Appendix 1. Assessment of cardiometabolic risk factors in each cohort

The ABCD study used a Leicester portable height measure (Seca, Hamburg, Germany) and a Marsden weighing scale (Model MS-4102, Rotherham, United Kingdom) to measure height and weight, respectively. WC was measured with a non-elastic measuring tape (Seca, Hamburg, Germany). BP was measured twice using an Omron 705 IT device (Omron Healthcare Inc, Bannockburn, IL, USA) in the supine position. If the two measurements differed >10 mm Hg, a third assessment was performed ¹. At ages 5 to 6 years, the overnight fasting blood samples were collected by the Lab Anywhere kit (Haarlem, The Netherlands) and analysed in the Regional Laboratory of Amsterdam. At ages 11 to 12 years, capillary blood was collected by finger puncture after 3 h fasting and analysed by the point-of-care analyser Alere Cholestech LDX machine using Lipid Profile and GLU cassettes (Cholestech Alere Health Hayward, CA, USA) ².

The Generation R study used standardized procedures to measure height and weight: underwear only and barefooted standing position. BP was measured at the right brachial artery, four times with one-minute intervals, using the validated automatic sphygmomanometer Datascope Accutor Plus TM (Paramus, NJ). The mean values for systolic and diastolic BP were calculated using the last three blood pressure measurements of each participant. Thirty-minutes fasting blood sample was analysed using the Cobas 8000 analyzer (Roche, Almere, The Netherlands) ³.

The Lifelines used a SECA 222 stadiometer and a SECA 761 scale to measure height and weight, respectively, without shoes and heavy clothing. BP was measured ten times during 10min with Dynamap, PRO 100V2. The fasting blood sample was collected and transported to the central LifeLines laboratory in Groningen for analyses ⁴. For all cohorts, BMI was calculated, and the mean value of BP measurements was used.

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Figure S1. Directed acyclic graph of the association between air pollution / green space exposure and change of cardiometabolic risk.

(1) ABCD study

(2) Generation R study

(3) Lifelines study

Figure S2. Correlation matrix of environmental exposures of children participating in three Dutch cohort studies. Green space was measured by the percentage of area devoted to green space within a Euclidean buffer of 1000 m around residential addresses. PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, and elemental carbon (EC) were based on data of a resolution of 25*25 m raster.

Table S1. Linear relation between air pollution, green space exposure (mutual confounded) and change of cardiometabolic risk factor clustering (MetScore)^{1,2}

Exposure	Change of MetScore in ABCD, n=2,547		Change of MetScore in Generation R, n=5,431		Change of MetScore in Lifelines, n=5,844	
	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i>	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i>	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i>
PM _{2.5} concentration	-0.001 (-0.007, 0.005)	0.76	0.0002 (-0.003, 0.003)	0.91	-0.001 (-0.004, 0.003)	0.71
PM ₁₀ concentration	-0.0003 (-0.006, 0.005)	0.90	0.0001 (-0.003, 0.003)	0.92	-0.002 (-0.005, 0.002)	0.41
NO ₂ concentration	0.001 (-0.005, 0.007)	0.72	0.001 (-0.001, 0.004)	0.37	0.006 (0.00001, 0.011)	0.05
Soot concentration	0.001 (-0.006, 0.008)	0.82	0.001 (-0.003, 0.004)	0.74	0.008 (0.001, 0.015)*	0.03
Green space density in 500 m buffer	-0.003 (-0.011, 0.005)	0.46	-0.0004 (-0.004, 0.003)	0.85	-0.001 (-0.003, 0.00001)	0.05
Green space density in 1000 m buffer	-0.007 (-0.014, -0.0005)*	0.04	0.001 (-0.003, 0.005)	0.59	-0.001 (-0.003, 0.0001)	0.07
Green space density in 2000 m buffer	-0.008 (-0.013, -0.003)**	0.002	-0.0005 (-0.004, 0.003)	0.77	-0.002 (-0.003, -0.0001)*	0.04

¹ Unit of air pollution is per SD based on data of a resolution of 25×25 m raster. Unit of green space is per SD. The SDs were 1.1, 1.4, 3.6, 0.2, 21.1, 20.6, and 19.0 for PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, elemental carbon, and green space in 500 m buffer, 1000 m buffer, and 2000 m buffer, respectively.

² Models adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, baseline MetScore, highest parental education level, maternal smoking during pregnancy, screen time, leisure time physical activity, parental marital status, year of birth, duration between two surveys, neighborhood socioeconomic status score, and urbanicity degree. Models of air pollution additionally adjusted for green space density in 1000 m buffer. Models for green space additionally adjusted for PM_{2.5} concentration.

P* < 0.05, *P* < 0.01, ****P* < 0.001

Table S2. Linear relation between air pollution, green space exposure and change of cardiometabolic risk factor clustering (MetScore)^{1,2}

Exposure	Change of MetScore in ABCD, n=2,547		Change of MetScore in Generation R, n=5,431		Change of MetScore in Lifelines, n=5,844	
	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i>	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i>	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i>
PM _{2.5} concentration	0.001 (-0.006, 0.007)	0.80	0.001 (-0.001, 0.003)	0.22	-0.0003 (-0.004, 0.003)	0.88
PM ₁₀ concentration	0.002 (-0.005, 0.008)	0.66	0.001 (-0.001, 0.003)	0.22	-0.001 (-0.005, 0.002)	0.52
NO ₂ concentration	0.002 (-0.004, 0.009)	0.43	0.001 (-0.001, 0.003)	0.29	0.006 (0.001, 0.010)*	0.01
Soot concentration	0.002 (-0.004, 0.007)	0.51	0.001 (-0.001, 0.002)	0.31	0.008 (0.002, 0.014)*	0.01
Green space density in 150 m buffer	-0.002 (-0.009, 0.005)	0.55	-0.002 (-0.005, 0.001)	0.17	-0.001 (-0.002, 0.0004)	0.16
Green space density in 250 m buffer	-0.001 (-0.008, 0.006)	0.70	-0.002 (-0.005, 0.001)	0.21	-0.001 (-0.003, 0.00003)	0.06
Green space density in 350 m buffer	-0.002 (-0.009, 0.006)	0.70	-0.002 (-0.005, 0.001)	0.25	-0.001 (-0.003, -0.00004)*	0.04
Green space density in 750 m buffer	-0.005 (-0.013, 0.002)	0.19	-0.001 (-0.004, 0.002)	0.54	-0.001 (-0.003, 0.0002)	0.08
Green space density in 1650 m buffer	-0.008 (-0.013, -0.003)**	0.004	-0.001 (-0.004, 0.002)	0.58	-0.001 (-0.003, 0.0001)	0.07

¹ Unit of air pollution is per SD based on data of a resolution of 1000 m raster. Unit of green space is per SD. The SDs were 1.0, 1.4, 3.7, 0.2, 21.9, 21.9, 21.3, 20.8, and 19.7 for PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, elemental carbon, and green space in 150 m buffer, 250 m buffer, 350 m buffer, 750 m buffer, and 1650 m buffer respectively.

² Models adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, baseline MetScore, highest parental education level, maternal smoking during pregnancy, screen time, leisure time physical activity, parental marital status, year of birth, duration between two surveys, neighborhood socioeconomic status score, and residence density.

P* < 0.05, *P* < 0.01, ****P* < 0.001

Table S3. Linear relation between air pollution, green space exposure (mutual confounded), and change of cardiometabolic risk factor clustering (MetScore)^{1,2}

Exposure	Change of MetScore in ABCD, n=2,547		Change of MetScore in Generation R, n=5,431		Change of MetScore in Lifelines, n=5,844	
	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i>	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i>	β (95% CI)	<i>P</i>
PM _{2.5} concentration	-0.0005 (-0.007, 0.006)	0.89	0.0003 (-0.002, 0.003)	0.77	-0.001 (-0.004, 0.003)	0.73
PM ₁₀ concentration	0.0001 (-0.007, 0.007)	0.97	0.0005 (-0.002, 0.003)	0.73	-0.002 (-0.005, 0.002)	0.42
NO ₂ concentration	0.001 (-0.006, 0.007)	0.85	0.002 (-0.001, 0.004)	0.14	0.006 (0.0004, 0.011)*	0.04
Soot concentration	0.0001 (-0.006, 0.006)	0.98	0.001 (-0.001, 0.003)	0.33	0.008 (0.002, 0.015)*	0.02
Green space density in 150 m buffer	-0.002 (-0.009, 0.005)	0.56	-0.001 (-0.004, 0.003)	0.61	-0.001 (-0.002, 0.0004)	0.16
Green space density in 250 m buffer	-0.001 (-0.008, 0.006)	0.72	-0.001 (-0.004, 0.003)	0.78	-0.001 (-0.003, 0.00002)	0.06
Green space density in 350 m buffer	-0.001 (-0.009, 0.006)	0.72	-0.001 (-0.004, 0.003)	0.66	-0.001 (-0.003, -0.0001)*	0.04
Green space density in 750 m buffer	-0.005 (-0.013, 0.003)	0.20	0.001 (-0.003, 0.005)	0.60	-0.001 (-0.003, 0.0001)	0.07
Green space density in 1650 m buffer	-0.008 (-0.014, -0.003)**	0.003	-0.00001 (-0.004, 0.004)	1.00	-0.001 (-0.003, 0.00004)	0.06

¹ Unit of air pollution is per SD based on data of a resolution of 1000 m raster. Unit of green space is per SD. The SDs were 1.0, 1.4, 3.7, 0.2, 21.9, 21.9, 21.3, 20.8, and 19.7 for PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, elemental carbon, and green space in 150 m buffer, 250 m buffer, 350 m buffer, 750 m buffer, and 1650 m buffer respectively.

² Models adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, baseline MetScore, highest parental education level, maternal smoking during pregnancy, screen time, leisure time physical activity, parental marital status, year of birth, duration between two surveys, neighborhood socioeconomic status score, and urbanicity degree. Models of air pollution additionally adjusted for green space density in 1000 m buffer. Models for green space additionally adjusted for PM_{2.5} concentration.

P* < 0.05, *P* < 0.01, ****P* < 0.001